

SPECIFIC CONSUMPTION DIFFERENTIATION: KOSHER AND HALAL CERTIFICATION

Benefits of a differentiated certification

1. Sheep grazing on Las Albaidas farm, Cordoba 2+3 Sheep grazing 4. Sheep breed Iojena, Loja, Granada

THE WHAT AND WHY

A differentiated sheep certification for Kosher and Halal markets is key to accessing specific, high-value niches. These certifications guarantee that the production process complies with strict religious requirements: Kosher, according to Jewish standards, and Halal, according to Islamic law. Each requires unique procedures for the slaughter, handling and monitoring of livestock, thus ensuring respect for the beliefs of consumers.

The differentiation allows producers to position themselves in growing global markets, such as the Middle East, Europe and North America, where these practices are an integral part of the culture. It also boosts consumer confidence, increases competitiveness and opens up trade opportunities. Implementing clear standards and reliable certificates reduces legal risks, improves traceability and ensures a supply chain aligned with ethical, cultural and religious values, thus maximising the profitability of the sheep sector.

Keywords: Certification, Halal, Kosher, Sheep, Marketing

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

In order to implement a differentiated sheep certification for Kosher and Halal, it is essential to comply with the specific religious requirements of each system.

Both certifications require full traceability, ensuring that livestock are handled and transported according to religious standards. It is necessary to train staff, implement specific quality controls and collaborate with recognised certifying bodies in each market. In addition to documenting the process, ensuring regular audits and complying with international and local regulations are key to obtaining and maintaining these certifications in order to open up niche markets.

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ADVANTAGES

Kosher and Halal certification in sheep offers multiple economic, commercial and social advantages and benefits by positioning producers in specialised, high-value niche markets. Both certifications ensure that production, handling and slaughter processes meet strict religious standards, which builds consumer confidence and increases competitiveness.

In the case of Felipe Molina, a Merino sheep farmer in the province of Córdoba, and Juan Antonio Moreno Cobo, in Loja, Granada, they are implementing the requirements of Kosher and Halal certification in order to expand their market and diversify their products. This means that it is possible to sell products at times when lamb consumption is lower in their area.

The economic and commercial advantages are numerous. Firstly, differentiation in certification gives access to international markets, as the demand for Kosher and Halal products is steadily growing, especially in countries in the Middle East, Asia, Europe and North America. These markets give value and require certified products, which significantly expands trade opportunities. Consumers in these niches are willing to pay a premium price for certified products, as they represent quality and cultural compliance.

By adopting both certifications, producers are able to supply both Jewish and Muslim communities, thus maximising their market reach. Reducing trade barriers by complying with religious regulations minimises legal risks and facilitates export to countries with strict Kosher and Halal food regulations.

Kosher and Halal seals give a competitive advantage over conventional products, differentiating the offer in a saturated market. Ensuring global standards improves the possibility of participating in international supply chains and working with large distributors.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Complying with religious standards reinforces the positive perception of the brand and ensures its long-term sustainability.**
- **Kosher and Halal seals give a competitive advantage over conventional products, thus differentiating the offer in a saturated market.**
- **Differentiation allows producers to position themselves in growing global markets, such as the Middle East, Europe and North America, where these practices are indispensable.**

Sheep breed lojeña, Loja, Granada

Sheep from the farm of Juan Antonio Moreno Cobo, in Loja, Granada

More Information(web):

<http://acrol.es> <https://www.acvovejalojena.es/> https://ganaderosyganaderasenextensivo.org_

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